

ADAPTATION OF STUDENTS TO PHYSICAL EXERCISES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation

Exercise has a specific positive effect on the young organism, while various unfavorable factors of the external environment, such as magnetic storm, oxygen deficiency, some toxic substances have their own bad effect on the development and formation of the spine

Key words

Exercise, young organism, efficiency, harmonic and functional development of the organism, adaptation, spine, development and formation.

Currently, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH.M.Mirziyoyev, large-scale work is carried out in our country to improve the management system in the field of physical education and sports, develop mass Sports, Select and educate talented spotters, strengthen the field with qualified personnel.

Exercise is an important place in the upbringing of a comprehensive, harmonious mature, active personality. Exercise. first of all, it assumes the rational organization of affairs, recreation, nutrition, physical activity, the rule of personal hygiene, family cohesion and the elimination of harmful habits. The great role in the formation of physical exercises of the younger generation is played by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 15, 2022 PF-52. Everyone needs to understand the need for physical education and sports so that they can physically educate themselves, and diligently form their health on the basis of a certain system of physical activities that they like.

Great German philosopher I. In his work, "the ability to overcome illness spiritually depends only on the power of desire", Kant sets out a program of self-discipline. According to his point of view, when a person rules over his nature, he does not rule over you. I. Kant was not in good health during his childhood and youth. Nevertheless, having worked on himself, that is, finding exercises suitable for his own organism, by the age of 40 his health had strengthened, and by the end of his life (Kant died at the age of 80) he maintained a high level of workability, not suffering from any diseases. A person, realizing the need to educate himself physically, should

pay attention to his organism and Health, choose sets of exercises that are suitable for his capabilities.

Exercise sets are selected depending on the structure of the torso, interest in one or another physical activity, client. The state of exhaustion is usually felt at the end of the day, which is due to the accumulation of impulses coming to the cranial shell, blood sugar, oxygen depletion and, finally, the accumulation of residues of metabolism in the body. Methods for eliminating the state of exhaustion are Turlich. The first is a long sluggish rest. unfortunately many choose this path. The second, a special medikamem. The consumption of drugs, they affect the activity of brain cells, weakening .

Body-adjusting exercises play an important role in the development and wellness of the whole organism and help to develop and strengthen large muscle organs such as the shoulder girdle, torso, legs, make joints mobile, normalize the process of muscle tension and relaxation. The task of these exercises is to correctly form the qaddi - Qom, strengthen the entire musculoskeletal apparatus and improve blood circulation, breathing, exchange processes, nervous system activity.

Exercises that adapt the body activate the work of the higher motor centers that control movements; help to show physical qualities such as speed, agility, strength ratio, endurance, flexibility, arouse a positive – emotional mood in a person. The body adaptation exercises given in a certain consistency are aimed at gradually attracting the whole organism to the state of activity, strengthening functional processes that contribute to its general vital activity. The first group of exercises is aimed at developing and strengthening the shoulder girdle and arm muscles. They help to expand and increase the scale of chest breathing: strengthen the diaphragm the entire respiratory musculature of the intercostal muscles, allow deep breathing, strengthen the back muscles, adjust the spine, help strengthen the heart muscles, optimize the rhythm of heart contractions.

The second group of exercises is focused on the development and strengthening of the torso, back muscles. These exercises affect the correct formation of the groin and help to develop the flexibility of the spine when bending the torso forward and to the sides, turning right, left, as well as in rotation. The main vase of the last exercise is to strengthen the pelvic position while playing the foot while sitting, sitting with the chord dry, or sitting with the legs backward (stationary position) while rotating the torso. The third group of exercises is intended to develop and strengthen the muscles of the legs and abdomen. They help strengthen the abdominal muscles, which prevent internal organs from shaking during intensive movements (jumps, jumps, etc.), and also prevent blood from running in the venous blood vessels. Thus, the set of exercises used has a comprehensively strengthening

effect on the children's body. At the same time, exercises that adapt an organism that requires accuracy, ingenuity, certain isolation and, at the same time, integrity educate attention, willpower, goal orientation, stagnation reactions, the ability to coordinate one's movement with the movement of the entire children's team, to be able to aim in space.

Each movement begins with the initial position: the correct position of the torso (standing), sitting, lying positions, and the necessary position of the legs and arms for a particular exercise.

- Preliminary position for the legs in a standing position: the main standing position – the heels are combined, the ends of the legs are pulled back (large groups). This position is used at the following times: before and at the end of the exercise (sometimes raised at the ends of the legs);

- Semi-climbing and full climbing (the back is adjusted, the knees are pushed to the sides, the heels are slightly raised);

- When lifting and bending the legs from the knee: when extending the legs forward, left, right, back.

- Slightly lagging legs - legs are retractable (leg surface, step width), leg ends are slightly spread out;

- Foot care (shoulder-width apart) foot tips are slightly curled; foot pairing foot tips and heels are put together. This position is used when climbing;

- Standing with legs-the first leg is placed in front of the second, the heels are placed parallel;

- Standing on the knees - knees, calves, the ends of the legs are resting on the floor, the ends of the legs are written-this position is used when twisting, sitting on the heel;

- Standing with the feet slightly backward at the foot surface width and the foot surface slightly towards the sides, but not inward. This condition is used in small groups.

It is recommended to carry out the following exercises on the formation of the Kaddi-qomat at home:

- 1.Children sit with a chord dry, when performing the exercise, it is necessary to bend forward and touch the head to the right left knee. With the help of hands, it is necessary to bend to the side and not raise the knee when performing the exercise, and after any exercise, keep the torso straight.

- 2.The practice of turning the torso to the right and left can be performed in a seated, standing, leg-written, shoulder-width apart position. Hands may also be at the waist, written on the side, behind the head.

3. Leaning forward in a sitting position, placing a piece of the hand on the floor to the right, left, and re-lifting it.

4. On the floor, sitting on the carpet, hands back, forming a support, raising and lowering the legs with the correct grip, passing both legs in pairs from the rope. Children should monitor that they do not have a bucrisimon when performing the exercise, do not squeeze their head on their shoulders.

5. From an upright position, the arms are stretched forward, sitting and standing exercises leaning against the wall. Leaning against the wall, this exercise is done back to the birnecha boron.

6. Standing in the initial position, swing the right or left leg and bring it forward (karate) at this point to play the bat under the foot. Kaddi-training to hold the hand correctly, shaking the leg with the right hand without bending forward.

7. In a sitting position on the carpet, stretch the legs forward, pull something with the paws, take it to the sides, pair the legs, raise. The family educator should observe that children are in the right movement of the shoulder, spine, head while performing these exercises.

8. Lifting and lowering the shoulder. When performing this exercise, children should observe that their head does not bend forward, that the shoulders do not turn forward, that they are not curled, and that the shoulder should be raised and lowered precisely to the top. Each set of physical exercises and activities for children should be carried out in agreement with the advice of the family doctor.

It is important that the family educator knows the purpose of each exercise performed. The development of the muscles of the body, first of all, the motor apparatus, blood circulation and the respiratory system, has a huge impact on the formation of the pacemaker. Therefore, when performing exercises with children, The Governess should pay attention to the fact that the children breathe, exhale.

Children perform exercises especially well, which are performed in the direction of music. The softness and expressiveness of movements increases. All this indicates that children are growing up with the opportunity to be able to freely control their actions, acting in a way that is fully consistent with the task of action received. It should be borne in mind that only if the physiological and emotional tasks in the exercises are changing, carefully mastered gymnastic exercises will pay off. That is why when choosing an exercise, it is important to consider that it is diverse, the scale and pace of movements it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that it changes, exercises are performed in different ways to get an assessment and to participate in the competition, and other similar parties. Exercises performed together teach children to correctly distribute their day, taking into account certain resistances that occur in it.

To the ways of adapting a young organism to physical exercises, Ibn Sina attached great importance in his works. Temperance is known to man from ancient times. Our goal is to explain the motivating factors and how to use them more. If the body remains to be adjusted even for a short period of time (before a trip to a long cold country), then it is enough to use several intensive training sessions in which a short-term cold affects. True, we cannot say that this hoi prevents no colds (flu)at all. But in the body, the tendency to squeak gradually increases. Getting acquainted with the essence of temperance, it is necessary to list its factors, such as water, sun, air, endowed by nature. In the cold, in the heat (water, air), tempering calms the body. In the process of tempering, it should be remembered that the colder (icy) the water, the longer its effect can also last 3-5 minutes. In this case, the specific aspects of each organism must be taken into account. Care should be taken when taking a sun bath. Otherwise, an offtob stroke can lead to a breakdown of nerve fibers.

The negative effect of sunlight: manifests itself in headaches, weakness, poor sleep, poor appetite, decreased work activity, burns of the skin of the body. Tanning in the sun passes mainly under the influence of ultraviolet rays contained in the sun. Under the influence of ultraviolet rays on human skin, the body develops vitamin “D” vitamin “D”, which in its place prevents rahit disease. Therefore, the moment of sunbathing is recommended from sunrise in the morning. Under the influence of ultraviolet light, the human organism develops vitamin “D”. As we know, vitamin “D” strengthens the bone.

References:

- 1.Ibragimovich, T. A. (2024). USE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES. IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI, 3(36), 53-58.
- 2.Ashurali, T., & Doston, R. (2023). Sports and Mass Events at the School. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 19, 83-88.
- 3.Tuychiev, A. I. (2022). TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF DISCIPLINARY SKILLS OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF GAMING TOOLS: Uychiev Ashurali Ibragimovich, Teacher of Fergana State University. Education and Innovative Research International Scientific and Methodological Journal,(2), 160-162.
- 4.Ibragimovich, T. A. (2023). WAYS TO ADAPT A YOUNG ORGANISM TO PHYSICAL EXERCISES. Conferencea, 289-297.
- 5.Туйчиев, А. И. (2023). ПЕДАГОГИКО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ У УЧАЩИХСЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНИРОВАННОГО ОТНОШЕНИЯ ЧЕРЕЗ ИГРУ. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 2(3), 62-66.

6. Tuychiyev, A. I. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF DISCIPLINARY SKILLS IN STUDENTS AS A KEY PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. Academic research in educational sciences, 3(2), 896-901.
7. Ashurali, T., & Doston, R. (2023). Sports and Mass Events at the School. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 19, 83-88.
8. Ibragimovich, T. A. (2022). Game Technologies and their Significance in the Development of Education of a Modern Teenager. Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT, 2(10), 7-12.
9. Туйчиев, А. И. (2023). ИГРОВЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ИХ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В РАЗВИТИИ И ВОСПИТАНИИ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ПОДРОСТКА. ИЖОДКОР О'QITUVCHI, 3(33), 17-22.
10. Umirov, S. (2022). PROFESSIONAL SPORTDA YUQORI NATIJALARNI BASHORAT QILISHDA IRSIY VA ORTTIRMA OMILLARNING AHAMIYATI. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(12), 100-103.
11. Umirov, S. B. (2023). NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research, 18, 133-137.
12. Umirov, S. (2023). JISMONIY-AQLIY RIVOJLANISHNING MOHIYATI VA OZIGA XOS HUSUSIYATLARI. Наука и инновация, 1(15), 123-127.
13. Umirov, S. B. (2023). NATIONAL STRUGGLE AS ONE OF THE TYPES OF PHYSICAL CULTURE. American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research, 18, 133-137.
14. Sidikova, G., & Sobirova, D. (2024, March). THE ROLE OF GYMNASTICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOVEMENT COORDINATION IN CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 39-44).
15. Sidikova, G., & Jamolov, S. (2023). AGE-SPECIFIC CHANGES IN THE INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(4), 60-67.

